

Reducing the Delay in Adaptive Streaming by Use of HTTP/2 Features

Bachelor's Thesis

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Abstract

HTTP-Based Adaptive Streaming (HAS) has been widely adopted for video streaming over the Internet, because it can serve a large variety of heterogeneous clients. Each client experiences different network conditions, which can rapidly change during a streaming session. Therefore, one of the main streaming challenges is adjusting the streaming settings in order to maximize Quality of Experience (QoE). QoE is defined as minimizing playback disruptions along with quality transitions while maximizing video quality [18]. Additionally, low latencies are required for live streaming. Streaming over HTTP requires the client to retrieve the video in form of segments from a server via HTTP requests. Hence, in live streaming a minimal delay of one segment duration is introduced because the request can only be sent when the segment is completely created. Reducing the segment duration allows segments to be delivered to the client sooner. Nevertheless, as a result of the increased number of requests, the added overhead has a negative impact on the video transmission. Moreover, reducing the segment duration implies having faster reaction time to fluctuations in bandwidth changes. We provide software components to reduce latency in live streaming sessions. To counter the overhead of reduced segment durations, we use the HTTP/2 Server Push and request cancelling features. The aim of this thesis is to reduce the usual delay of 30 seconds during live transmissions to under 5 seconds.

Zusammenfassung

HTTP-Based Adaptive Streaming (HAS) wird mittlerweile standardmäßig für Video Streaming über das Internet verwendet, da es unabhängig vom Client funktioniert. Für jeden Client ergeben sich unterschiedliche Netzwerkbedingungen, die sich während der Videoübertragung rapide verändern können. Aus diesem Grund ist eine der Hauptproblemstellungen, sich an diese Netzwerkbedingungen anzupassen, um eine möglichst hohe Quality of Experience (QoE) gewährleisten zu können. QoE bedeutet Qualitätswechsel und Unterbrechungen beim Abspielen des Videos möglichst gering zu halten. Gleichzeitig soll bei der Wiedergabe eine maximale Qualität gesichert werden [18]. Beim Streaming von Live-Inhalten ist zusätzlich eine geringe Latenz von beachtlicher Bedeutung. Beim Streamen über HTTP wird dem Client das Video in Form von Segmenten über HTTP-Responses geliefert. Beim Live-Streaming existiert eine Mindestverzögerungszeit mit der Dauer einer Segmentlänge, da das Segment erst gesendet werden kann, nachdem es vollständig erstellt wurde. Das Reduzieren von Segmentlängen erlaubt es, Segmente dem Client schneller liefern zu können. Die erhöhte Anzahl an Requests hat jedoch eine negative Auswirkung auf die Übertragung des Videos. Außerdem kann aufgrund der Reduzierung der Segmentdauer schneller auf Schwankungen in der verfügbaren Bandbreite reagiert werden. Es werden Softwarekomponenten zur Reduktion der Verzögerungen beim Streaming von Live-Inhalten vorgestellt. Um den Overhead von verkürzten Segmentlängen auszugleichen, werden HTTP/2 Server Push und Request Cancelling Features eingesetzt. Das Ziel dieser Arbeit ist die Reduktion des üblichen Delays von 30 Sekunden beim Live Streaming auf fünf Sekunden zu reduzieren.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Recently, there has been an unprecedented increment in video consumption. Of all consumer Internet traffic in 2015, video streaming contributed 70% and it is expected to reach a peak of approximately 80% by 2020 [6]. The preferred video content delivery method over the Internet is HTTP-Based Adaptive Streaming (HAS) [29]. It profits from the existing Content Delivery Network (CDN) infrastructure, including caches and proxies, without any needed modification. Thus, there is no need to have dedicated video servers. Furthermore, streaming based on HTTP is also scalable because servers are not required to maintain client sessions.

Video content may be divided into two main categories, Video on Demand (VoD), which refers to pre-recorded content, and live video. There are a number of differences between live video and VoD. According to [11], average bitrate is more critical in live sessions than in VoD sessions. Moreover, while latency in VoD has a greater margin, the necessity of a low delay transport during live streaming becomes crucial to achieve a stream with the lowest possible latency and hence offer an acceptable Quality of Experience (QoE). QoE refers to minimizing playback disruptions along with quality transitions while maximizing video quality. Also, minimizing the playback latency becomes a primary factor for live streaming. *Live latency* is defined as the time interval between the live event and client-side playback [35]. Reducing latency in video streaming requires optimization in the process of delivery, as for instance, not delivering a better video representation than the one the client can display.

Videos are delivered to the client in segments of equal duration. To deliver each video segment, the client must send a request to the server. As a result, one part of the bandwidth is used for the overhead of exchanging requests and responses to deliver a video. An approach to reduce this overhead would be to increase the segment duration. In terms of HTTP, the risk of wasting bandwidth due to session abandonment is too high [38]. A long segment duration can lead to a lack of flexibility for the client's bitrate adaptation. In contrast, a low segment duration benefits the flexibility of the bitrate adaptation during the streaming. There is a tradeoff between flexibility and overhead that comes with modifying the segment duration. The overhead coming from a low segment duration is known as *request explosion* [35].

Recently, multiple efforts have been made to implement different Adaptive Bitrate Stream-

ing (ABS) techniques, such as Apple HTTP Live Streaming (HLS), Microsoft Smooth Streaming (MSS), Adobe HTTP Dynamic Streaming (HDS), and Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (MPEG-DASH). The only internationally standardized technique is MPEG-DASH [19]. MPEG-DASH has gained relevance over the last couple of years as an effort to unify all different ABS techniques. It is a common effort between multiple individuals and conglomerates to collaborate together in a constantly maintained and developed technology. This effort allows everyone to profit from a standard that unifies technologies that otherwise would be exclusive to a company. One of the main advantages of MPEG-DASH is its flexibility because it is codec agnostic and also highly customizable in settings [27].

Normally during a live streaming session, the user streaming bitrate adaptation algorithm has to tolerate latencies of approximately 30 seconds. With Low-Latency Prediction-Based Adaptation (LOLYPOP), latency gets reduced to 5 seconds. However, the goal of this thesis is to improve that mark with use of sub-second segment duration in combination with HTTP/2 improvements. Sub-second segments introduce more sensitivity to throughput variations and rapid reaction to network changes.

Video conference with active and passive participants

The main intended use case for this thesis is a video conference where participants are divided into active and passive. Active participants participating in the conversation and passive participants act as listeners. Passive participants can become active and vice versa. While active participants demand latencies lower than 100 milliseconds, passive ones can tolerate higher latencies. Passive participants will use MPEG-DASH based on Transmission Control Protocol (TCP). Active participants, however, will use User Datagram Protocol (UDP) based protocols, e.g. RTP Control Protocol (RTCP) or Real-time Transport Protocol (RTP) among others. Guaranteeing scalability while delivering video content with a low live latency are the main criteria for this system.

The further chapters of this thesis is structured as follows: In Chapter 2, the concepts to be used in this thesis are introduced. In Chapter 3, our approach to lower the delay in Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (DASH) live streaming sessions is described. Subsequently, our test setup is defined in Chapter 4. In Chapter 5, the evaluation results are analyzed. Finally, in Chapter 6 we present our findings during the evaluation.

Chapter 2

Background

In this chapter technical and theoretical concepts required to understand the later discussion about the topic will be reviewed. First, background information on HAS will be provided. Afterwards, the new HTTP/2 features will be covered. The evaluation setting will be discussed on Chapter 3. Further on, we will talk about MPEG-DASH and finally about QoE.

2.1 Video

2.1.1 Video Coding

In this section basic video coding concepts are introduced in order to explain the metric taken for the evaluation section later. We will also explain the different challenges faced during video coding and how our decision was taken in taking certain methods.

Video *coding* is a general term to refer to video *encoding* and *decoding*. A video codec is a program that encodes and decodes video data [24]. Video encoding is the process of converting raw video data, for instance frames, into a compressed digital video format. A compressed version of the raw video data improves the efficiency of the transmission. The video coding format and the encoding parameters have a strong impact on image quality and latency. Depending on the video coding format, the compression can be lossy or lossless. During a live event transmission, content must be encoded live to be sent to the client. A slow coding process can lead to an increased live latency.

Group of Pictures

Each segment consists of a series of interframes and intraframes, also known as Group of Pictures (GOP), which optimize video decoding. GOPs contain one or multiple Stream Access Points (SAPs) to enable the client to switch representation at these points. A representation is an encoded version of the same video with different encoding parameters. Each representation has a different bitrate to adapt better to the client's current network conditions. At the beginning of each segment, an Intra-coded frame (I-frame) is placed, containing a full

frame, after which a series of Bi-predictive coded frames (B-frames) and Predictive coded frames (P-frames) follow to enable video compression. B-frames contain information based on the I-frame in the same GOP [37]. They are only fully decodable with the help of the previous I-frame. The most compressed representation should contain a single GOP, so that only an I-frame is included. One of the reasons not to use only one GOP for a video is that it is strongly related to delays in HTTP [35]. Each HTTP request delivers a segment, which can only be delivered when fully formed. Therefore, in a video streaming session the delay is of at least one segment duration.

2.1.2 Measuring Video Quality

Video quality is challenging to define, because it could either be defined based on the viewer's perception, subjectively, or by considering mathematical equations, objectively [25]. Objective measures may not always reflect the viewer's perception. There are multiple alternatives to measure image quality in a video, e.g. Structural Similarity (SSIM) or Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR). SSIM is considered to be more perception-oriented [15]. We decided to measure quality objectively using PSNR, because perception is relative. PSNR, defined in equation 2.1, outputs the similarity between two images of dimensions $m \times n$ as a numerical factor. Image quality is measured in how similar is an image compared to the original one. The higher the PSNR value, the better the quality of the compared image. PSNR is defined over Mean Squared Error (MSE), defined in equation 2.2.

$$\text{PSNR}(f,g) = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \frac{255^2}{\text{MSE}(f,g)} \quad (2.1)$$

$$\text{MSE}(f,g) = \frac{1}{m \cdot n} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (f_{ij} \times g_{ij})^2 \quad (2.2)$$

Average PSNR

The PSNR formula used for the average PSNR calculation is the YUV-PSNR [26], which takes the different weights on each of the YUV color space (YUV) components into account to get the average.

A color space is a particular representation of an image's color information. The YUV represents the color space of an image in one brightness component, Y , and two chrominance components, U and V . The Y component contains the main information of the image [31]. The representation of the properties of an image in YUV color space allows efficient encoding of the image [10]. We calculate the PSNR using the YUV components of the compared images. The definition of the YUV-PSNR formula is shown in 2.3.

$$\text{YUV-PSNR} = \frac{6 \cdot \text{Y-PSNR} + \text{U-PSNR} + \text{V-PSNR}}{8} \quad (2.3)$$

Correlation between video properties

Reducing delay in video streaming starts at video coding. There are multiple approaches and factors that can be taken into account regarding video coding. Three factors have here especially been taken into consideration:

- Bitrate
- GOP size
- Video quality

These three variables can be modified to achieve different goals. A valid approach is to hold constant GOP size, video quality and consider bitrate as a variable to discover what is necessary to achieve the same quality. The approach in this thesis is to play with different GOP sizes while holding the bitrate constant to analyze its impact on video quality due to the compression loss at the moment of video coding.

2.2 HTTP-Based Adaptive Streaming

HTTP is widely adopted for streaming purposes. Nevertheless, streaming without ABS would not be able to serve the vast heterogeneity of clients and their network conditions. Often, streaming would stall if the client is not able to adapt to the current changing network conditions during a session. Rebuffering has a negative impact on user engagement [11]. HAS tackles the challenge of heterogeneity of clients by offering different representations of the same video, the client then selects the video representation that best fits his current network conditions. HTTP also offers the ability of reusing existent CDN, alleviating the problem of dedicated video servers. Without special modifications a normal content server can be used for streaming purposes. Knowing the disadvantages of using HAS is a key point in addressing its problems. Buffering in a video streaming session in HAS is a common problem, which according to [11] has the most severe impact on user engagement.

Figure 2.1 illustrates the common architecture for a HAS environment in which the server contains multiple representations of the same content. The term content representation refers to the same content encoded with different parameters. Different bitrates allow to adapt better to the client's streaming bandwidth. On the right hand side of the image, the requested video bitrates by the client along the streaming session in correlation with the network bandwidth are displayed.

2.2.1 Quality of Experience

The term QoE was first introduced as a user-oriented quality metric [23]. In this thesis we use the LOLYPOP definition of QoE [18] based on three aspects:

- Playback interruptions

Figure 2.1: HAS architecture

- Selected video quality during the streaming session
- Quality changes during playback

Additionally, in live streaming minimizing the delay has an impact on QoE.

2.2.2 MPEG-DASH

MPEG-DASH, also DASH, is as of August 2022 the only international standard regarding video streaming. The MPEG-DASH specification was released in 2012 [19]. According to the standard, at the beginning of the streaming session the client receives a Media Presentation Description (MPD) file containing all representations available of the content on the server. Depending on the network conditions and the available content representations on the server, the client requests different representations while streaming to avoid video stalling and rebuffering.

2.2.3 LOLYPOP

LOLYPOP is an adaptation algorithm developed to reduce transport latency [18]. The algorithm allows the client to skip segments, taking into consideration the number of quality transitions, to achieve this. Normally in a DASH setup, the client starts streaming a certain bitrate. In case of a change in the network conditions, the client switches representations iteratively instead of choosing the representation that best fits the current Internet connection. LOLYPOP enables non-iterative quality transitions. The algorithm calculates the representation of the next segment to download in a streaming session in function of:

- Target live latency (Δ)
- Number of skipped segments ($\Sigma^* \in [0, 1]$)
- Number of quality transitions ($\Omega^* \in [0, 1]$)

2.2.4 Integration of LOLYPOP in dash.js

dash.js is a streaming client developed by DASH Industry Forum (DASH-IF) members and an open source community under [7]. The dash.js client comes with the Near-Optimal Bitrate Adaptation for Online Videos (BOLA) [28] algorithm already integrated. In the evaluation, the LOLYPOP [18] algorithm is used. The algorithm was integrated into dash.js by Armand Zangue. It is available under [9].

2.3 HTTP/2

HTTP/2 is the new revised version of HTTP by Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) released in May 2015 [4]. It is based on the SPeedy (SPDY) protocol, an initiative started and developed by Google with the aim of making the web faster and more efficient [3]. In May 2016, Google announced that they would drop support for SPDY in favor of the standardization of the new version of HTTP. HTTP/2 based many of its features on the second version of Google's protocol, SPDY/2, but includes additional modifications and improvements. Currently, all major browsers support HTTP/2.

The main features of HTTP/2 are:

- Server Push
- Request cancellation
- Multiplexing
- Header Compression (HPACK)

With the new features of HTTP/2 a tradeoff has been made between scalability and speed. Scalability is reduced in comparison to the previous versions. The introduction of the *Server Push* feature favors speed with the condition of becoming stateful. This feature requires the server to maintain a persistent connection with the client to push all the required resources during a session. Although HTTP/2 itself does not require encryption [4], as of August 2022 all browsers require encryption according to [21].

To lower overhead in each communication step, HTTP/2 introduced HTTP frames, a minimal unit of exchanging information [4]. Frames are classified according to their purpose. We will focus on two frames that enable of the HTTP/2 features: They will be discussed in Section 2.3.2. These are:

- PUSH_PROMISE
- RST_STREAM

We will now illustrate a request exchange in HTTP between server and client, where the client sends a request to the server for each resource. In Figure 2.2 this exchange is exemplified. The previous versions of HTTP are referred to as HTTP/1.x to avoid listing every subversion of the first series of HTTP.

Figure 2.2: HTTP/1.x example communication between server and client

2.3.1 Multiplexing Connections

HTTP/2 uses multiple concurrent streams over a single TCP connection. The maximal number of concurrent streams can be set in order to avoid clogging the connection for long periods of time. Multiplexing solves the TCP Head-of-Line (HoL) blocking problem in HTTP/1.x. HoL blocking occurs in TCP because only one packet can be transmitted at a time. Thus, the communication queue is occasionally held by the transmission of large packets.

2.3.2 Server Push

In this version of HTTP, the server can define additional content for a certain request, which might be later retrieved by the client. Based on the additional content, the server may push responses to the client. The client can indicate the server, on the request's headers, that Server Push should be disabled. Pushing preserves the same-origin policy from HTTP/1.1 [4]. To avoid unnecessary client requests for pushed content, the server sends *push promises* upon receipt of the client's request. Push promises are defined by the standard as a PUSH_PROMISE frame. Promises indicate the client what content is about to be pushed.

The server usually is aware of files that may be requested by the client additionally to a certain request. For example, in order to view a website, the client will request an html file. Additional files will be necessary, for instance, the styles and the scripts corresponding to that website. According to our example, the server will have something similar to a dependency tree illustrated in Figure 2.3. An example of the dependencies linked to the website that shall

be requested from the client can be found in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Dependency tree for requested segments

Using HTTP/2 the server can take advantage of the dependency tree to make the communication more efficient by avoiding additional requests from the client to each resource and pushing these additional resources. In Figure 2.4, an example usage of frames is shown. Frames do not include full headers and are therefore more efficient than sending full responses [4]. In this case, the push promise frame is used to signalize the client which content will be additionally sent. Without this measure the client cannot know which resources are about to be sent and therefore bandwidth could be wasted by requesting resources repeatedly. It is important to be careful when using this feature, because despite of its promised gains in efficiency, when not used properly it can make the communication more inefficient than with HTTP/1.x [20].

Figure 2.4: Example of the HTTP/2 Server Push feature

2.3.3 Cancelling Requests

The client can cancel content pushing for multiple reasons, e.g. it has already received the content about to be pushed. In that case, the client would have to notify the server of such decision. For that purpose a *RST_STREAM* has to be sent with the error code *CANCEL* [4]. The ID of the stream to be cancelled is required to send an *RST_STREAM*.

In Figure 2.5, an alternative example of the Figure 2.4 with the client having the resource already in the browser’s cache and therefore cancelling the push promise of the file with the same name, is shown. Thus, the server will not send that file pushed to the client and will proceed to push the other resources according to the dependency tree in Figure 2.3 that were not cancelled. The client has to be HTTP/2 compatible and it has to have the directive to accept pushed content activated. Otherwise, if the client explicitly denies all push content the server will not be able to push any content to it.

Figure 2.5: Example of the HTTP/2 Push feature and cancelling

2.4 Delay

Delay, as defined in [17], is explained with Figure 2.6. This figure was taken and adapted from [17]. The horizontal axis represents time. For a segment i with duration τ , *live latency* (Δ) is defined as the time interval between happening of the live event ($i\tau$) and its *playback deadline* ($i\tau + \Delta$). The *transport delay* ($\Delta - \tau$) is defined as the time that a video segment on a medium needs until it is delivered to the client.

Figure 2.6: Delay model

Chapter 3

Reducing the Delay by Use of HTTP/2 Features

In this chapter we present our approach to reduce latency in live streaming sessions based on reduced segment duration as proposed in [18]. In [16] it is shown that the overhead caused by reducing segment duration can be countered by use of HTTP/2. A similar approach has been regarded in this thesis by using HTTP/2 to reduce latency. The main differences between this thesis and previous work can be resumed as follows:

- Client-side use of LOLYPOP implemented in dash.js hosted on [9].
- Customizations to the DASH-IF DASH Live Simulator (DLS) hosted in [8].
- Cancellation of pushed promises by a proxy when switching representations.
- Sub-second segment duration to reduce minimal live latency.

In Table 3.1 the segment durations used for the experiments are shown.

Segment duration
500 ms
750 ms
1000 ms
2000 ms

Table 3.1: Segment durations used for encoding

3.1 MPEG-DASH Content

In order to test the implementation in the customized dash.js [7] version of the video streaming client, MPEG-DASH content must be prepared as well. No specific customization was

made to the client in order to test the HTTP/2 features. From the encoded video in eight available resolutions we generated different MPEG-DASH content sets for the tests to cover a wide range of scenarios. We mostly focused on content sets with a small segment duration, because, as of August 2022, we could not find any adaptive bitrate streaming test where content sets with a duration under one second were used. It is rather uncommon to use a short segment duration because of the overhead coming with when using HTTP without the Server Push feature introduced in HTTP/2 [35].

The MPEG-DASH content preparation process can be resumed in three steps:

1. Video preparation: adding a H.264/ MPEG-4 Advanced Video Coding (H.264/MPEG-4 AVC) container.
2. Video encoding: at the end of this step a MPEG-4 (MP4) container is created.
3. Video segmentation and MPD creation.

3.2 Client Setup

The dash.js client has limited access by Google's API to the network layer which contains specific information about the protocols used and its technical details. As an example, Google's APIs (APIs) do not offer as of August 2022 any form of knowing the stream ids to the client. For that reason, a client proxy was used to cancel push promises when needed.

3.2.1 Client Proxy

In order to have access to the protocol details and still be able to cancel requests, the client uses a proxy to communicate with the server which will be responsible for cancelling and forwarding everything between both parties. This architecture is illustrated in Figure 3.1.

The proxy has been modified to cancel all pending push promises after each representation switch. The customized proxy is hosted on [30].

Figure 3.1: Client communication with server through proxy

3.3 Server Setup

3.3.1 DASH-IF DASH Live Simulator

Simulating the same live streaming session for testing purposes can become a difficult task, considering that many factors influence the outcome. Some of them are generated randomly during runtime. For this reason, we use DLS that simulates VoD to live content. By doing so, we are able to reconstruct a live streaming session over and over again and observe different aspects of it under the same conditions. We also have more control over the parameters for each session.

We use a customized version of DLS hosted on [8]. It includes the following modifications:

- HTTP/2 Server Push support
- Wait for segment availability
- Accept sub-second segment durations

The Web Server Gateway Interface (WSGI) allows web applications to interact with web servers. DLS makes use of this interface to modify requests and simulate the live content. The DLS runs using `mod_wsgi`, which is the name of the Apache module that acts as a WSGI to enable python code to interact with the Apache server. In Figure 3.2, we illustrate the DLS interaction with the server over the WSGI.

Figure 3.2: DLS architecture

3.3.2 Server Push Strategy

Server Push strategies define when the resources should be pushed for efficient use of bandwidth. In [35] three Server Push strategies are presented:

- *No Push*
- *All Push*
- *k-Push*:

We use the k -Push strategy, which consists of pushing k segments to every client's request. To avoid the over-push problem mentioned in [35], we decided k to be three. As the segments are named sequentially, we push the next k sequentially named segments, in the same video quality as the one requested, when the client requests segment n .

In Section 3.2 and 3.3, the modifications used for the client and the server were introduced, these are summarized in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Client communication with the server through a proxy

Chapter 4

Evaluation Environment

In this chapter we will explain step by step the environment in which the evaluation was carried out. We will talk about video file preparation, video encoding, MPEG-DASH content generation and server setup.

4.1 Video Preparation

We ran the tests using the 14 minutes 48 seconds long animated movie Sintel [12]. The selection of the test video was based on raw video data availability. A lossless copy of the frame by frame video was used to encode the video. Next, we generated MPEG-DASH content with short duration. The film was downloaded in form of 21,312 frames. The frames were provided as Tagged Image File Format (TIFF) with 16 bits per channel (bpc); bits per channel indicate the number of bits that define the color of a pixel.

While encoding the Sintel movie to 144p resolution, we encountered a problem. A video in 144p resolution corresponds to a height of 144 pixels. The Sintel movie has an Aspect Ratio (AR) of 2.35:1, its AR corresponds to a width of 338.4 pixels. A pixel is the smallest representable unit on a screen [13]. Therefore, the width and height in pixels cannot have decimals. An alternative is to take the nearest integer from 338.4. This would result in a different AR than the original movie and than the other representations used for the evaluation. That could result in complications for the dash.js player because having a different AR than the rest ends up with a separated adaptation set in the MPD file. In order to keep the original AR, we encoded the video with the dimensions of a 240p representation but with the bitrate from the 144p representation.

Originally, the video was encoded as well in 250 ms but we decided to focus more on the longer segment durations because of possible bitrate adaptation problems with the LOLYPOP dash.js client. In this section we will only include figures from the Sintel representation with segment duration of 500 ms to illustrate some facts. In Figure 4.1, the bitrate distribution of every segment within every encoded representation is illustrated. The additional figures, qualitatively identical to Figure 4.1, are shown in Appendix D.

Figure 4.1: Frames bitrate of Sintel 500ms representation. Horizontal line: median; box: quartiles; whiskers: 0.5 and 0.95 quantile; flier points: outliers.

4.2 Video Encoding

The video was encoded from original frames in order to achieve the desired bitrates for higher resolutions. For this purpose the x264 utility [33] was used to encode eight movie representations with different resolutions. The compression format used was H.264/MPEG-4 AVC [37]. The used encoding parameters, resolutions and bitrates in the tests were taken from [2].

In Figure 4.3, the computed bitrates are listed. The specific targeted bitrate in kilobits per second (kbps) for each resolution are shown in the Table 4.1. The difference between targeted and computed bitrate is explained in [36]. The width and height of each representation is the result of the height as the resolution and the width derived from the movie ratio of the Sintel movie of 2.35:1. Therefore, the width of each representation is calculated as $height \cdot resolution$.

The audio bitrate is not shown in Table 4.1 because it stays constant across all representations. The reason to encode only one audio representation is that a low audio quality has a more negative impact on users than a lower video quality [5]. The audio used for the evaluation part has an average computed bitrate of 132.43 kbps.

The video encoding process can be summarized in the following four steps.

1. Create a video H.264/MPEG-4 AVC container from the Sintel movie frames
2. Create MP4 file from H.264/MPEG-4 AVC container

3. Video fragmenting
4. Video segmentation and MPD file creation

First, the H.264/MPEG-4 AVC container is created from TIFF frames with the parameters from Table 4.2. Then, the MP4 file is created from the H.264/MPEG-4 AVC raw video container, from which fragmenting is done. Finally, after the video is fragmented, it is segmented and transformed into the MPEG-DASH specification.

Representation number	Targeted bitrate in kbps	Resolution	width x height
1	91	240p	564 x 240
2	180	240p	564 x 240
3	469	360p	846 x 360
4	978	480p	1128 x 480
5	2058	720p	1692 x 720
6	3953	1080p	2538 x 1080
7	9581	1440p	3384 x 1440
8	21373	2160p	5076 x 2160

Table 4.1: Targeted video bitrates and resolutions

The encoding parameters for x264 are listed in Table 4.2. Some parameters in Table 4.2 were taken from [2]. The bitrates were adapted from [2] to achieve an exponential difference between each representation. Usually, video does not maintain a constant bitrate throughout the segments. The video buffering verifier (vbr) was created by Moving Picture Experts Group (MPEG) as a measure to constrain the bitrate peaks between segments [32]. In streaming sessions, it helps to ensure that the buffer does not overflow or underrun. The parameter *keyint* specifies the maximum frame interval between keyframes. The *video-filter* parameter references width and height as X and Y respectively. These variables correspond to the width and height stated in Table 4.1. In Table 4.3 the parameters for adding the MP4 container with *mp4box* are shown.

In the third step *fragmenting* is done with the command-line utility *mp4fragment*. Fragmenting consists of dividing a video into multiple sequences without creating additional files. In Table 4.4 the parameters used for the video fragmentation are shown.

In the fourth step conversion to the MPEG-DASH standard and segmentation is done. The parameters used for *mp4dash* are shown in Table 4.5. The resulting bandwidth values from *mp4dash* do not reflect the original bitrates from the video files. The program calculates the required bandwidth, roughly double the actual bitrate, to prevent stalling during a video streaming session. In live streaming this knowledge is not available in advance because the video data is generated during the streaming session. Hence, we adjusted the resulting bitrates to match the bitrates from the encoded video data. To obtain the actual bitrate, file size was divided by the video file duration. The bandwidth values before and after the correction are located in Appendix C.

key	value
fps	24
tune	psnr
psnr	
preset	slow
bitrate	<i>see Table 4.1</i>
vbv_maxrate	$2 * \text{bitrate}$
vbv_bufsize	$2 * \text{bitrate}$
keyint	<i>segment duration in seconds * fps</i>
min-keyint	<i>segment duration in seconds * fps</i>
scenecut	0
pass	1
video-filter	resize:width=X,height=Y

Table 4.2: x264 encoding parameters

key	value
add	<i>H.264/MPEG-4 AVC container</i>
fps	24

Table 4.3: mp4box parameters to add MP4 container to H.264/MPEG-4 AVC container

key	value
fragment duration	<i>duration in ms from table 3.1</i>

Table 4.4: mp4fragment parameters to fragment MP4 file

key	value
profile	live
mpd-name	Manifest.mpd

Table 4.5: mp4dash parameters for conversion to the MPEG-DASH standard and segmentation

4.2.1 Quality Loss during Video Encoding

While encoding in certain resolutions, data was lost compared to the original frames. The data loss was measured with the PSNR, which was explained in the background section. We calculated the PSNR between every encoded video frame and original version. Figure 4.2 shows that with decreasing segment duration the PSNR of each representation also decreases. In other words, the quality decreases with lower segment durations because of the loss of image compression.

Figure 4.2: Average PSNR of the encoded Sintel movie representations

4.2.2 Resulting Bitrate after Video Segmentation

With reduced segment duration, the video compression rate sinks as we can observe in Figure 4.3. During a streaming session the client should be able to change the current video resolution dynamically based on the current network conditions. Adapting to the current network conditions is possible by requesting the next segment in a higher or a lower resolution to avoid any playback interruptions. Video segments are standalone GOP composed by an initial I-frame. Initial I-frames are encoded as IDR-frames (IDR-frames) in H.264/MPEG-4 AVC so that they contain complete frame information and enable fast decoding and switching. Each I-frame, which equals an uncompressed frame, is followed by multiple compressed P-frames and B-frames that contain the difference between the initial and the actual frame. Thus, they can only be uncompressed using the I-frame from its segment. As a result, it is required that every video segment starts with an I-frame. Changing the actual video resolution received from the server is only possible on segment start.

On one hand, a higher segment duration favors video compression by reducing the amount of I-frames. Higher segment durations also restrict the flexibility of changing the video resolution on network changes. On the other hand, a lower segment duration implicates a higher number of uncompressed I-frames at every segment start having a negative impact on the movie compression rate. It is a tradeoff between compression rate and segment duration.

In a streaming session each video segment is treated as a standalone HTTP request. Thus, additional overhead comes as a result of the increasing HTTP request number when shortening the segment duration. One request must be made for each desired video segment. This can be bypassed with the HTTP/2 Server Push feature.

Figure 4.3 illustrates the difference of the targeted bitrate compared to the resulting bitrate

caused by the segment duration of each representation. The bitrate in kbps is on a logarithmic scale. In Figure 4.4, we show the evaluation parameters for each test case.

Figure 4.3: Average Bitrate

4.3 Evaluation Setup

Figure 4.5 shows the final test setup. Another client was used to generate background traffic to add realism to the test results. This way, we can test with additional delays to the network as it would happen on a real life environment. We conducted the tests in the TKN Wireless Networks Testbed (TWIST) testbed at the Technische Universität Berlin [14]. An Access Point (AP) was used to connect the client with the server via WLAN.

LOLYPOP	Protocol		Segment duration	
$\Delta = 5$ $\Sigma = 50\%$ $\Omega = 4\%$	HTTP/1		500ms	
			750ms	
			1s	
			2s	
	HTTP/2	No Push		500ms
				750ms
				1s
				2s
		Push k = 3	No Cancel	500ms
				750ms
			Cancel	1s
				2s
		500ms		
		750ms		
		1s		
		2s		

Figure 4.4: Evaluation parameters

Figure 4.5: Evaluation architecture

Chapter 5

Evaluation Results

This section provides the evaluation of segments of short duration combined with HTTP/2 features to avoid *request explosion*. Additionally, as a client we use the customized version of dash.js with LOLYPOP integrated and an enhanced version of DLS, as explained in Chapter 3.

The client used for the tests is the dash.js client by DASH-IF. We used Google's Chrome browser, version 54.0.2840.71 (64-bit), to run the client. The evaluation was conducted using 2 GHz WLAN between the AP and the client. SSL encryption was used between the server and the client to enable the HTTP/2 features. Although encryption is not required by the HTTP/2 standard, browsers do require encryption to use the new HTTP version. However, encryption is known to slow down the streaming [20].

Our experiments on the client-side are conducted on a 64-bit Linux computer with the following technical specifications:

- Intel Core i5-3210M @ 2.5 Gigahertz (GHz)
- Intel Ivybridge Mobile Graphics
- 2×32 KB L1 caches, a 256 KB L2 cache and a 3 MB L3 cache
- Ubuntu 16.04 LTS

The technical specifications of the server, 64-bit Linux, are the following:

- Intel Core i7-3770 CPU @ 3.40GHz
- 256 KB L1 cache, 1 MB L2 cache and a 8 MB L3 cache
- Ubuntu 16.04 LTS

Each test was run five times for five minutes.

LOLYPOP parameters

Constant LOLYPOP parameters for the evaluation were used. The focus was on reducing live latency with reduced segment duration and with use of HTTP/2 features. We used $\Sigma = 0.5$, $\Omega = 0.4$ and $\Delta = 5$ seconds.

Chrome's Bug

The evaluation could not be completed because after observing the evaluation results, we detected an HTTP/2-related bug in Google's Chrome browser. In HTTP/2, the browser should recognize when the client, in this case dash.js, requests a video segment that has been pushed already. The browser should then respond with the previously pushed resource, fetching it from the cache and hence, cancelling the client's request to the server. Figure 5.1 depicts the expected communication between client and server more detailed than Figure 2.5. In Appendix 1, a minimal working example in Javascript is included to reproduce this issue.

Figure 5.1: Expected behavior in Chrome when requesting a video segment that was pushed before by another request.

During the evaluation we could observe that Chrome does not always respond with the requested file from the cache. This causes an increased overhead because some segments were transmitted twice. Thus, the increased overhead in the live video streaming session had a negative impact on the delay. Figure 5.2 illustrates the case where Chrome fails to intercept the client's request. The bug report for this incident can be found under [1].

Figure 5.2: Actual behavior in Chrome when requesting a video segment that was pushed before by another request.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

In this thesis the problem of reducing latency in live streaming is addressed. We take advantage of HTTP/2 features to reduce the overhead impact on latency of using sub-second segment durations to reduce minimal live latency. We implemented a client-side proxy to cancel pending push promises when switching representations. Additionally, the LOLYPOP implementation in dash.js is used for the client. Due to the fact that HTTP/2 is based on Google's SPDY protocol, the modified dash.js client was run in Google's Chrome browser. The aim was to reduce live latency to less than 5 seconds by pushing segments from the server to the client to improve efficiency in bandwidth usage. However, we could not take advantage of the evaluation environment because a bug in Chrome strongly increased the live delay during the live video streaming. Chrome failed to deliver resources from the cache when they were requested by the client. In future work, we plan to implement the client's decision to cancel pending push content based on its performance impact.

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Appendix A

Acronyms

HTTP Hyper Text Transfer Protocol	
SPDY SPeeDY	7
CDN Content Delivery Network	1
VoD Video on Demand	1
QoE Quality of Experience	1
HoL Head-of-Line	8
TCP Transmission Control Protocol	2
MPEG-DASH Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP	2
HLS HTTP Live Streaming	2
HDS HTTP Dynamic Streaming	2
MSS Microsoft Smooth Streaming	2

APPENDIX A. ACRONYMS

TCP Transmission Control Protocol	2
UDP User Datagram Protocol	2
RTP Real-time Transport Protocol	2
RTCP RTP Control Protocol	2
URI Uniform Resource Identifier	71
HAS HTTP-Based Adaptive Streaming	1
DASH Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP	2
MPD Media Presentation Description	6
CORS Cross-Origin Resource Sharing	
WSGI Web Server Gateway Interface	15
MP4 MPEG-4	14
API Application Programming Interface	14
MPEG Moving Picture Experts Group	19
DASH-IF DASH Industry Forum	7
IETF Internet Engineering Task Force	7
DLS DASH-IF DASH Live Simulator	13

TWIST TKN Wireless NetworkS Testbed	22
LOLYPOP Low-Latency Prediction-Based Adaptation	2
BOLA Near-Optimal Bitrate Adaptation for Online Videos	7
H.264/MPEG-4 AVC H.264/ MPEG-4 Advanced Video Coding	14
ABS Adaptive Bitrate Streaming	1
AR Aspect Ratio	17
PSNR Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio	4
MSE Mean Squared Error	4
SSIM Structural Similarity	4
TIFF Tagged Image File Format	17
bpc bits per channel	17
vbv video buffering verifier	19
AP Access Point	22
SAP Stream Access Point	3
YUV YUV color space	4
GOP Group of Pictures	3

APPENDIX A. ACRONYMS

IDR-frame Instantaneous Decoding Refresh frame	21
I-frame Intra-coded frame	3
P-frame Predictive coded frame	4
B-frame Bi-predictive coded frame	4
GHz Gigahertz	25
kbps kilobits per second	18

Appendix B

Code

Listing 1: Javascript minimal working example of Chrome's HTTP/2 bug

Appendix C

Tables

Segment duration	Representation with resolution	Video		Audio		Unit	Ratio actual to computed bandwidth in mp4dash	
		Actual	computed in mp4dash	Actual	computed in mp4dash		Video	Audio
500ms	240p	97686	188873	128032	136695	bps	1:1.9	1:1.1
	240p	193256	372743				1:1.9	
	360p	505427	964863				1:1.9	
	480p	1050820	1966202				1:1.9	
	720p	2216430	4704041				1:2.1	
	1080p	4257200	8539075				1:2	
	1440p	10306550	19919917				1:1.9	
	2160p	22802140	45011935				1:2	

Figure C.1: Bandwidth correction from mp4dash output for segment duration 500ms

Segment duration	Representation with resolution	Video		Audio		Unit	Ratio actual to computed bandwidth in mp4dash	
		Actual	computed in mp4dash	Actual	computed in mp4dash		Video	Audio
750ms	240p	96970	181599	128032	134217	bps	1:1.9	1:1
	240p	190910	354025				1:1.9	
	360p	499990	930174				1:1.9	
	480p	1039150	2285928				1:2.2	
	720p	2191370	4781440				1:2.2	
	1080p	4202870	9343217				1:2.2	
	1440p	10209990	20257575				1:2	
	2160p	22573270	42033864				1:1.9	

Figure C.2: Bandwidth correction from mp4dash output for segment duration 750ms

Segment duration	Representation with resolution	Video		Audio		Unit	Ratio actual to computed bandwidth in mp4dash	
		Actual	computed in mp4dash	Actual	computed in mp4dash		Video	Audio
1000ms	240p	96130	176791	128032	134425	bps	1:1.8	1:1
	240p	188950	343992				1:1.8	
	360p	496370	935740				1:1.9	
	480p	1031390	2119940				1:2.1	
	720p	2177320	4424524				1:2	
	1080p	4169930	8472304				1:2	
	1440p	10152200	18874561				1:1.9	
	2160p	22475890	42254724				1:1.9	

Figure C.3: Bandwidth correction from mp4dash output for segment duration of 1 second

APPENDIX C. TABLES

Segment duration	Representation with resolution	Video		Audio		Unit	Ratio actual to computed bandwidth in mp4dash	
		Actual	computed in mp4dash	Actual	computed in mp4dash		Video	Audio
2000ms	240p	93480	159258	128032	135015	bps	1:1.7	1:1.1
	240p	184920	318336				1:1.7	
	360p	488070	863869				1:1.8	
	480p	1018420	1868056				1:1.8	
	720p	2148520	3888468				1:1.8	
	1080p	4102010	7133139				1:1.7	
	1440p	10057630	18329478				1:1.8	
	2160p	22214830	39004062				1:1.8	

Figure C.4: Bandwidth correction from mp4dash output for segment duration of 2 seconds

Appendix D

Plots

Figure D.1: Average bitrate of Sintel 250 ms representation

Figure D.2: Average bitrate of Sintel 500 ms representation

Figure D.3: Average bitrate of Sintel 750 ms representation

Figure D.4: Average bitrate of Sintel 1000 ms representation

Figure D.5: Average bitrate of Sintel 2000 ms representation

Figure D.6: Frames bitrate of Sintel 250 ms representation

Figure D.7: Frames bitrate of Sintel 750 ms representation

Figure D.8: Frames bitrate of Sintel 1000 ms representation

Figure D.9: Frames bitrate of Sintel 2000 ms representation

Appendix E

Client

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E.1 Skipping segments in LOLYPOP dash.js

The LOLYPOP dash.js streaming client includes the feature of skipping segments for segment with a duration of two seconds. In this thesis I use different segment durations as specified in Section 3 Table 3.1. Skipping segments in LOLYPOP dahs.js is done by using dummy segments which simulate real segments during streaming. I had to modify the segment skipping mechanism for segments with a duration of 1 second, 750 milliseconds and 500 milliseconds.

E.1.1 Adding Missing Features to LOLYPOP dash.js

I modified the testing environment of LOLYPOP dash.js to evaluate all the scenarios described in Chapter 4 Section 4.2 Figure 4.4. The modified files to customize the test environment in the player are the following:

- `samples/live-streaming/lolypop.html`

- src/streaming/utis/DummyFragment.js
- src/streaming/utis/SegmentData.js
- tools/evaluate.py
- tools/logserver.py

E.2 HTTP/2 Access in dash.js

Initially, the mechanism to cancel unspent HTTP/2 Server Push promises was to be implemented into the dash.js streaming client as shown in Figure E.1. In the figure, the client requests the first video segment in the first quality representation and it receives the push promise for the second video segment, in this case the *k-Push* parameter is set to one on the server. After receiving the first segment, the client decides to switch representation on the second segment. The client should then cancel the unspent push content from the server and continue with the streaming. Unfortunately, Chrome does not have APIs to trigger HTTP/2 request cancelling. Therefore, I opted to use a client-side proxy to manage the push promises and pushed content.

E.3 Proxy

I used a proxy as an alternative to cancelling pending push promises when the client switches representations in a streaming session. The expected behavior of the proxy is exemplified in Figure E.2. I used the `nhttp2` library because it is one of the only HTTP/2 proxy implementations as of August 2022 with support for Server Push. The library includes multiple programs which makes the difficulty level higher for new developers. There is a documentation of the library but it does not cover the module architecture and interaction between the diverse classes.

Unfortunately, the `nhttp2` proxy module does not support cancelling unspent Server Push promises by the server when switching video quality during a streaming session. Therefore, I had to program this feature into the proxy. The configuration file used for the proxy is displayed in Listing 2.

Listing 2: Configuration parameters for `nhttp2`

E.3.1 Design

The design principle of the `nhttp2` library is the following:

- Modular software design is implemented.

Figure E.1: Expected request exchange if the client could manually trigger cancelling of unsent HTTP/2 Server Push promises

Figure E.2: Proxy behavior with cancelling pending HTTP/2 Server Push feature

- Shared classes for the proxy (*nghttpx*), the server (*nghttpd*) and the client (*nghttp*).
- The *nghttpx* component can function as a reverse or as a forward proxy.

In this section I will only cover the files relevant for the cancellation of HTTP/2 Server Push promises in *nghttpx*. The files written in italics are the files that I modified for the integration of the new feature in *nghttpx*.

- **src/shrpx_***
Files with the *shrpx* prefix are proxy components.
- **src/shrpx_http2_upstream.h**
Header of the HTTP/2 upstream component. The proxy classifies the communication streams between the proxy and the server and between the proxy and the client into upstream and downstream respectively. In this header the variables to store the last and the current client's request path are declared. Also, a variable to store a vector with the pending push promises is declared. The declared variables are summarized in the following list:
 - **std::vector<int>** *promised_stream_ids*
 - **std::string** *last_requested_video_representation_*
 - **std::string** *current_requested_video_representation_*
- **src/shrpx_http2_upstream.cc**
Implementation of the HTTP/2 upstream component. In this class the received pushed promises and sent pushed content are monitored to calculate the pending push content. The cancellation is done in this component inside the *on_downstream_header_complete* function with help of the *nghttp2_submit_rst_stream* function for every pending push promise.
- **lib/nghttp2_session.{h, cc}**
Component to store the details of a HTTP/2 session.

E.3.2 Initial Setup

The commands to compile the library are shown in Listing 3. Afterwards, the proxy can be run typing *nghttpx* in the command-line.

Listing 3: Compilation commands for the *nghttp2* library. The commands must be run from the root directory of the library.

E.3.3 Adding Missing Features to nghttpx

Cancellation of pending push promises

The push promises are monitored in the proxy to add received push promises sent from the server and delete already sent pushed content to the client. The proxy also monitors the current and the last representation selected by the client to trigger the cancelling of all pending push promises when it detects a representation switch.

API Specification

To implement the cancelling feature into the proxy no additional function was created. To modify the implemented behavior the following functions in *src/shrpx_http2_upstream.cc* must be inspected:

- **int Http2Upstream::on_downstream_header_complete**
I implemented the detection of video representation switch from the client during a streaming session and triggers the request cancellation of all unsent Server Push promises by the server to the client.
- **int on_frame_send_callback**
When the push content is delivered related to a push promise, I programmed the nghttpx proxy to remove the Server Push promise from the unsent push promises stored by the proxy in *int Http2Upstream::submit_push_promise*.
- **int Http2Upstream::submit_push_promise**
I store every push promise sent to the client in order to keep track of the pending Server Push promises.

Appendix F

DASH Live Simulator

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At the beginning of a DASH streaming session, the client requests the *Manifest.mpd* from the server. I configured the server to redirect the requests to the DLS. The simulator then returns a modified version of the VoD Manifest file for the requested video content to the server. The server then proceeds to return the Manifest file modified for live streaming to the client. Figure F.1 shows the trace of requests when using the simulator.

The live content was configured to be streamed using the infinite configuration of the simulator. The DLS offers three different configurations for live content availability.

1. Infinite
2. Time-limited
3. Multi-period

I used the infinite configuration of the simulator which simulates a stream since the Linux *Epoch Time*. Thus, during a live streaming session the client requests segment numbers which are not physically available on the server. The segment numbers requested are translated to actual segment numbers for the server to deliver to the client. The translation is done by the file *DashProxy*, located under *dashlivesim/dashlib/dash_proxy.py*. *DashProxy* is

Figure F.1: DLS versions on the server

the main interface of the simulator. In this file, the simulator determines if the segment was requested too soon, too early or in time.

Encryption is mandatory for browsers to communicate with the HTTP/2 protocol. When establishing a connection with the simulator via HTTPS, the first request was made with encryption and the rest of the session was made via HTTP. After analyzing the problem and the communication between client, simulator and server I discovered that the simulator was not setting the base URL properly in the dynamically generated MPD file. The simulator has a flag in *dashlivesim/dashlib/mpdprocessor.py* named *SET_BASEURL* which is per default set to true. When the flag is set to false the simulator sets the base URL of the MPD to the base URL of the request. In case the flag is set to true, it sets the base URL taking into account different parameters. I had to set the flag to false for the simulator to include the request's HTTPS protocol in the MPD file and thus, force the client to make the following requests using HTTPS.

F.1 Design

The design principle of the DLS is the following:

- The simulator can be used as an Apache mod_python plugin or as using mod_wsgi.
- Single entry point depending on how the simulator is used.

- Modular software design is implemented. Each functionality is implemented in classes that are called from the entry point.
- In the entry point the request is received, processed by the DLS and returned from the same function where the entry point is found.

In this section I will only cover the main project structure needed to understand the core functionality of the DLS using Apache mod_wsgi. The files written in italics are the files that I modified to include the additional features mentioned in Section F.3.

- *dashlivesim/mod_wsgi/mod_dashlivesim.py*
Entry point to the simulator. In this class a global flag is included which toggles the HTTP/2 support in the simulator. In this file the HTTP/2 module is called before exiting the DLS.
- **dashlivesim/vodanalyzer/**
Directory of classes to analyze VoD content.
- *dashlivesim/dashlib/dash_proxy.py*
Definition of class DashProvider which instantiates all subcomponents. In this class I added the feature of waiting for segment availability.
- *http2/push_headers.py*
Component which dynamically specifies the content to be additionally pushed to each segment request. This component is not available in the default version of DLS. I programmed it to add HTTP/2 support to DLS. Its functionality will be covered in Section F.3.3.
- *dashlivesim/dashliv/configprocessor.py*
Class which retrieves the configuration file for a requested resource and configures the live stream for VoD resources. In this class I added the support for sub-second segment durations. Segment duration was originally of type *int*, I changed the data type to float. This way, the simulator could retrieve the segment duration from the configuration file correctly.
- *dashlivesim/dashlib/mediasegmentfilter.py*
Class which translates a live segment number into a VoD segment number. In this file I prevented an error where segments could not be found caused due to the change of segment duration to float.
- *dashlivesim/dashlib/mpdprocessor.py*
Class which converts the static MPD to a dynamic one. In this class I changed the default behavior of setting the base URL to enable HTTPS in the entire streaming session.

Figure F.2: DLS Module Architecture

- **tools/run_vodanalyzer.sh**

Script to generate configuration files of live content.

A simplified architecture of the simulator, without any customization, is displayed in Figure F.2. Files and functions are abstracted as DLS Components. When the client wants to make a request to the simulator, the request is received by the server and then forwarded to the simulator. In the simulator, depending on the type of content requested by the client, the simulator proceeds to call different classes. For instance, when a Manifest is requested, the *MpdProcessor* class is called to translate the VoD Manifest to a live one. The default structure of the Dash Provider class is displayed in F.3.

F.2 Initial Setup

Preparation of VoD to live content for DLS

I first encoded the video as VoD and subsequently, VoD content was simulated as live content for the evaluation. This allowed me to reproduce the test scenarios and adjust parameters during the live streaming session with DLS. The video content must be configured to work with the DLS.

To prepare the VoD content for live simulation, I had to follow 4 steps:

1. **Apache2 mod_wsgi configuration**

The configuration file to activate DLS with mod_wsgi had to be moved from the simulator's source code directory to the Apache2 directory. The *mod_wsgi_dashlivesim.conf*

Figure F.3: Dash Provider architecture without modifications

WSGIScriptAlias	Wait for segment availability	Accept sub-second segment durations	HTTP/2 Server Push support
livesim_dashif	No	No	No
livesim_http1_custom	Yes	Yes	No
livesim_http2	Yes	Yes	Yes

Figure F.4: DLS versions on the server

specifies the directory for VoD configuration files and the directory for the video content in form of environmental variables. The environmental variables set in the configuration file are *VOD_CONF_DIR* and *CONTENT_ROOT*. The configuration also specifies the path to the source code of the DLS, as a *WSGIScriptAlias*, and the URL to the simulated content.

I specified multiple *WSGIScriptAliases* in the configuration file in order to use different versions of the simulator on the same server. Depending on the URL accessed by the client, the server uses the corresponding simulator from the ones specified in the settings. I modified the DLS to support three new features. The features are available depending on the URL the client uses to access the DLS. Three DLS versions are supported on the server, these are listed in Figure F.4.

Additionally, to avoid CORS issues with the video streaming client, another configuration file must be added to the Apache2 configurations. Listing 4 shows the bash commands to configure the server.

Listing 4: DLS settings for Apache2 Server

2. **Generation of live configuration files**

The DLS configuration files are used to parse the properties of each VoD content resource. Listing 5 displays the command for the creation of the live configuration files. The command had to be run for the content in each segment duration which contained the different representations. I had to adjust the segment duration for each generated configuration file. The script in DLS failed to recognize and set the actual segment duration in the configuration.

Listing 5: Configuration of live content

3. **Relocation of live configuration files**

The configuration files are generated in the directory of the DLS but they need to be accessed according to the environmental variable `VOD_CONF_DIR`. I had to relocate them to match the path of the environmental variable set in Apache2 in step one.

4. **Modification of live configuration files**

Without any modification the DLS does not accept sub-second segment durations. For media content with a sub-second segment duration the configuration file must be modified. When generating live configuration files the simulator sets a wrong segment duration for sub-second durations. Thus, it has to be manually corrected.

F.3 Adding Missing Features to DLS

I implemented three additional features in the DLS to reduce the live latency. Not every functionality of the simulator is documented. Therefore, I had to analyze the source code to understand the communication flow of the HTTP requests between the server and the simulator. The description and developer documentation of the modifications I made can be found below.

F.3.1 Wait for segment availability

During live streaming sessions content has a pre-defined availability time. The availability time defines the time interval where the client is allowed to request each segment. Thus, the DLS can throw two types of error related to the segment availability when requesting a segment. The request can either arrive too late or too early. If the request is made too early by the client, I configured the DLS to sleep for the time difference between segment availability time and request time. Subsequently, the simulator continues to deliver the segment as soon as it becomes available. This feature is necessary for the HTTP/2 Server Push feature.

The first attempt to integrate this feature was to call the entry point in the Dash Provider module after waiting with a modified request time when the segment first becomes available. The recursive call of the function that handles the request with the modified parameters

Figure F.5: Dash Provider architecture with support for waiting for segment availability

caused the buffer to stall during the stream. Therefore, the second attempt was to wait inside the function that handles the requests and directly from there trigger the sending of the requested segment without the use of recursion.

The architecture of the modified version of the Dash Proxy component to enable waiting for segment durations is shown in Figure F.5. The implemented functionality waits for segment availability when they are requested too early and sets the request time to a valid request time to deliver the segment to the client.

F.3.2 Accept sub-second segment durations

The MPEG-DASH standard supports sub-second segment durations in media content. Due to the fact that the simulator is developed by DASH-IF, I expected the simulator to fully support the MPEG-DASH specifications. However, the simulator does not accept sub-second segment durations. The files that were modified for this feature are listed in Section F.1.

F.3.3 HTTP/2 Server Push support

The HTTP/2 specification defines the functionality of the Server Push feature without specifying implementation details [4]. There is little documentation to software on pushing of requests to the client. There are two possibilities two activate the push feature:

1. Use an HTTP/2 server implementation alternative to Apache that also supports Server Push and specify the files in the server according to the implementation details.
2. Define the content to push as *Link headers* in the HTTP responses with Relation Type *preload* [22, 34]. When the Apache module `mod_http2` is activated, the server inspects

Figure F.6: DLS Module Architecture with HTTP/2 Module

the response headers before sending the response and if the Link header with preload Relation Type is included in the response the server will push the resources to the client automatically. Link headers can be set statically via `mod_headers` or dynamically by the application, in this case DLS. In Listing 6 a Link header is displayed where a segment should be sent to the client using HTTP/2 Server Push.

Listing 6: Example of Link header with Relation Type preload

The architecture of the customized version of DLS with HTTP/2 Support is shown in Figure F.6. The HTTP/2 Server Push component modifies the response headers after the DLS has finished processing the response and before it is sent to the client. In the response headers it signals the server the content to be pushed.

API Specification

The API only describes the HTTP/2 module that I integrated into the simulator.

Requirements for the HTTP/2 module

The media segments must be numbered sequentially.

- **add_push_headers(headers, url, k=3)**
Adds the next 'k' resources to be pushed to the response headers. This headers are then processed by the server in order to send the corresponding resources.

– Parameters

- *headers*: DLS response headers.
- *url*: Requested URL by the client.
- *k*: Number of segments to be pushed along with the requested resource. Default value is three.
- **Returns**
- Response headers with the addition of the segments to be pushed to the response.
- **process_url(*url*)**
Process url and return its main parts.
 - **Parameters**
 - *url*: Requested URL by the client.
 - **Returns**
 - A dictionary with the following attributes:
 - * *base_url*: Trimmed url from the beginning until last occurrence of a slash character, including last slash found.
 - * *resource_name*: Name of requested resource without extension.
 - * *ext*: Extension of requested resource.
- **format_header_link(*base_url*, *resource*)**
Format push resource for headers
 - **Parameters**
 - *base_url*: Trimmed url from the beginning until last occurrence of a slash character, including last slash found.
 - *resource*: Name to the resource to be pushed.
 - **Returns**
 - A single link element of the resource to be pushed that will be added to the response headers.

Figure F.7: Architecture of DLS HTTP/2 Module

Appendix G

Server

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On the server side basic configuration was needed to install and support the HTTP/2 protocol. The specific steps to enable the same configuration used for the server in Chapter 4 will be covered in this chapter.

G.1 HTTP/2

To enable HTTP/2 support for Apache Servers, the module `mod_http2` must be installed. With the module parameters can be tuned to improve the HTTP/2 performance. Server Push content can be defined statically in the Apache Server or it can also be dynamically defined via WSGI in the DLS. Statically defined because the configurations on the Apache will be loaded upon restart of the server. For a live streaming session with HTTP/2 Server Push support, the segments to be pushed to each segments could either be defined explicitly in the server configuration or it could be dynamically defined with python in a more flexible way without the constraint of having to restart the server after a Server Push content configuration change.

G.1.1 Installation

The Apache HTTP/2 module `mod_http2` is not included in Ubuntu 16.04 LTS because it is considered experimental as of August 2022. There are two alternatives to support HTTP/2 when `mod_http2` is not included in the distribution. The first alternative is to download an updated version of Apache which includes the module. The second alternative is to download the missing module and to install it. I decided to download the missing module for the default version of Apache included in the Ubuntu 16.04 LTS distribution. Listing 7 shows the necessary steps to download the module for an Apache Server in Ubuntu 16.04 LTS. The Apache version downloaded was 2.3.23.

Listing 7: Enable `mod_http2` in Apache

G.1.2 Configuration

After downloading the module and installing it, the Apache Server must be configured to take advantage of the HTTP/2 protocol. The configuration steps are the following:

1. Enable HTTP/2 via the Protocols directive. In the Apache configuration, *apache2.conf*, it must be specified that the server accepts both cleartext and secure HTTP/2 negotiation.
2. Restart the Apache Server
3. Source the Apache environmental variables *envvars*. After upgrading the server the *envvars* were not loaded.

G.1.3 SSL

Because all major browsers require encryption to use HTTP/2, as described in Section 2.3 in the Background Chapter, encryption must be enabled on the server. The commands to enable the SSL module in Apache are displayed in Listing 8. Additionally, SSL certificates must be created for the server. This will not be covered in this section.

Listing 8: Enable SSL encryption in Apache

G.2 Access Point Configuration

For the evaluation environment an AP was used to make the server available to the client via WLAN. I wrote a script to configure the AP to activate its wireless interface, and to forward the wireless connection to LAN, where the server was connected. The script to configure the AP is shown in Listing 9.

Listing 9: Configuration of live content

Appendix H

Video Preparation

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The DASH standard requires the media data to have an MPD file, in which the folder structure of the content is specified. The folder structure allows the client to know the Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) of the segments to request along the streaming session. Because the VoD content was simulated as live content, additional steps in the video configuration were necessary.

The parameters for step one to four are explained in chapter 4 section 4.2. The video preparation consisted of four steps:

1. Create a video H.264/MPEG-4 AVC container from the Sintel movie frames
2. Create MP4 file from H.264/MPEG-4 AVC container
3. Video fragmenting
4. Video segmentation and MPD file creation

H.1 Wrong encoding parameters

The parameters for table 4.2 were taken from [2, p. 20]. However, after encoding the video I noticed an error in the reference video encoding parameters. The parameter *keyint* defines

the maximum frame interval between keyframes for the H.264/MPEG-4 AVC container. In other words, *keyint* is defined as the number of frames in each GOP. Segment duration and frames per second correlate directly to the *keyint* count. This was not specified in the original parameters where *keyint* was defined as a constant. *keyint* is calculated with the formula $keyint = segment\ duration\ in\ seconds * fps$. As a result, the video data had to be re-encoded from the beginning for every video in each representation with the corresponding segment duration. Additionally, audio had to be encoded again for each segment duration. In total, thirty two video and four audio files were re-encoded. The files were encoded using a server with technical specifications listed in Chapter 5. The re-encoding process with the server specifications mentioned lasted two weeks.

H.2 Exponential bitrate distribution

The bitrates for each video representation were chosen with an exponential distribution. Originally, the video bitrate for the second representation was 369 kbps [2]. Figure H.1 shows the non-exponential bitrate growth between representations given the logarithmical bitrate axis.

As shown in figure H.2, the bitrate for representation 2 was then adjusted from 369 kbps to 180 kbps in order to achieve an exponential growth.

H.3 MP4 Container

The second step of video preparation comprises the conversion of the H.264/MPEG-4 AVC container to the MP4 format. Originally, the conversion was done with *mp4box*'s latest available version at the time of encoding, version 0.6.1, but I noticed that playing the converted MP4 resulted in intermittent video playback. In other words, the video stopped for short periods of time during playback.

To analyze the generated MP4 file, the *Bento4* library was used. The *Bento4* library includes a command-line tool called *mp4info* to inspect MP4 containers. By inspecting the file with *mp4info* no inconsistency could be detected with *mp4info*. Only after analyzing the video with the *mp4box* alternative, *ffmpeg*, it was evident what was the cause of the repeated playback interruptions. The MP4 container was inspected with the command exemplified in Listing 10. I discovered with *ffmpeg* that *mp4box* was setting the start time of the video 0.083044 seconds instead of 0 seconds. Therefore, the video was drifting out of sync repeatedly.

The bug that caused the wrong start time in the MP4 container is fixed in *mp4box* version 0.6.2. The parameters for the container format conversion are displayed in Chapter 4 Table 4.3. A file generated with *mp4box* version 0.6.1 is attached in this thesis for reference.

Listing 10: *ffmpeg* file inspection command

Figure H.1: Average bitrate of Sintel 500 ms representation with the original bitrate for representation 2 (369 kbps)

Figure H.2: Average bitrate of Sintel 500 ms representation with the corrected bitrate for representation 2 (180 kbps)

H.4 Required Bandwidth

During step four, in which the video is prepared for MPEG-DASH compliance, the Manifest used for the streaming is created with mp4dash. By default, mp4dash ignores the actual bitrates of each representation and sets the bandwidth values representation displayed in the MPD to a value called *required bandwidth*. The required bandwidth specifies the bitrate in bits per second needed to ensure continuous playback on the client. For live videos no information in advance of the rest of the streaming because data is generated on the fly. Although the parameters for mp4dash include the live MPD profile, the required bitrate was used for the MPD. Because the calculation and behavior of the required bitrate is not documented in mp4dash, I had to contact the developers to get information on the unexpected behavior.

H.5 Amending generated MPEG-DASH content

In Bento4 library version v1.5.0-611 the generated content does not include the *contentType* attribute for adaptation sets. Without this attributes the DLS version 1.4 cannot play the content specified in the MPD generated by mp4dash. This had to be manually added for each Adaptation Set in each of the MPD files generated.

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